

Theoretical studies on the vibrational spectra, detonation properties, and stabilities for adamantyl nitrates

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Abstract : 16 Adamantyl nitrates (ANs) have been theoretically studied to search for novel potential high energy density compounds (HEDC). The assigned infrared spectra of the ANs were obtained by the DFT-B3LYP method with 6-31G** and 6-31G* basis sets. The frequencies of symmetric stretching vibration of nitrate group for ANs have a hypsochromic shift with the numbers of nitrate group. Similarly, the frequencies of asymmetric stretching vibration have a same trend. The detonation velocity, pressure, and heat were estimated by the Kamlet-Jacobs formula. The stabilities of ANs were studied by the bond dissociation energy (BDE) and the energy level difference calculation. The number of the nitrate group is in direct proportion to the detonation properties. Conversely, it is in inverse proportion to the stability. Consequently, we should balance the stability with energy and density when a new molecule is designed.

Keywords : Detonation properties, vibrational spectra, stability, adamantyl nitrates, density functional theory.

Introduction

As one novel kind of high energy density compounds, organic cage compounds have focused the world's attention for several decades. The typical examples are CL-20 (hexanitrohexaazaisowurtzitane) and ONC (octanitrocubane). Adamantane (Scheme 1) is one cage hydrocarbon compound, which is composed of 10 carbon atoms and 16 hydrogen atoms with a large density and a high heat of formation. Recently, one type of adamantane derivative, polynitroadamantanes (PNAs), which possess large energy-density and excellent stability, has being extensively interested¹⁻⁹.

Scheme 1. Structure of adamantane.

Gilbert *et al.*¹⁰ calculated the density, heat of formation, and detonation pressure for a series of PNAs, which the number of nitro groups range from 2 to 16. Pivina *et al.*¹¹ predicted the properties of the isomers of hexanitroadamantane. Sýkare and Sućeska¹² estimated the detonation parameters for 1,3,5,7-PNA. All above

detonation properties are calculated by using the group additivity method. Xu *et al.*¹³ investigated the vibrational spectra, thermodynamic properties, detonation properties, and pyrolysis mechanisms for PNAs with the number of nitro groups ranging from 1 to 10 by using DFT-B3LYP/6-31G* method and Kamlet-Jacobs equation. They recommended 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10-PNA as the target of HEDM with insensitivity.

In view of -ONO₂ as one useful energetic group, we design 16 adamantanes derivatives with -ONO₂ groups (Table 1) in this present work. Subsequently, the molecular orbit, IR spectrum, density, enthalpy of formation, detonation properties, and bond dissociation energy (BDE) are calculated on the basis of optimized structures, and the stability is further analyzed.

Calculation method :

DFT B3LYP method with 6-31G** and 6-31G* basis sets were carried out to optimize structures and calculate molecular orbits and IR spectra for 16 ANs using Gaussian 09 program¹⁴. The molar volume of each molecule was calculated by the Monte-Carlo method, followed by

$$\rho_{\text{crystal}} = a \left(\frac{M}{V_m} \right) + b(\nu\sigma_{\text{tot}}^2) + c$$
 formula to obtain its den-

Table 1. Abbreviation and chemical name of 16 ANs

C1	1,3,5,7-Adamantyl tetranitrate	C9	2,2,4,4,6,6-Adamantyl hexanitrate
C2	2,4,6,8-Adamantyl tetranitrate	C10	1,2,3,4,5,6,7-Adamantyl heptanitrate
C3	2,2,4,4-Adamantyl tetranitrate	C11	2,2,4,6,8,9,10-Adamantyl heptanitrate
C4	1,2,3,5,7-Adamantyl pentanitrate	C12	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-Adamantyl octanitrate
C5	2,4,6,8,9-Adamantyl pentanitrate	C13	2,2,4,4,6,6,8,8-Adamantyl octanitrate
C6	1,2,3,4,5,7-Adamantyl hexanitrate	C14	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9-Adamantyl nonanitrate
C7	1,2,3,5,6,7-Adamantyl hexanitrate	C15	2,2,4,4,6,6,8,8,9-Adamantyl nonanitrate
C8	2,4,6,8,9,10-Adamantyl hexanitrate	C16	1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10-Adamantyl decanitrate

sity. The gas phase enthalpies of formation of ANs were derived from an isodesmic reaction. Subsequently, the sublimation enthalpies were calculated by formulae (1)-(5) to further achieve their enthalpies of formation for the solid phase.

The isodesmic reaction is as follows.

$$\Delta H_{\text{sub}} (298 \text{ K, kcal/mol}) = aA^2 + b(v\sigma_{\text{tot}}^2)^{0.5} + c \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{tot}}^2 = \sigma_+^2 + \sigma_-^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m [V^+(r_i) - \bar{V}_s^+]^2 + \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n [V^-(r_j) - \bar{V}_s^-]^2 \quad (2)$$

$$v = \frac{\sigma_+^2 \sigma_-^2}{[\sigma_{\text{tot}}^2]^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{V}_s^+ = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m V^+(r_i) \quad (4)$$

$$\bar{V}_s^- = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n V^-(r_j) \quad (5)$$

The detonation velocity, pressure, and heat were estimated by the Kamlet-Jacobs formula.

The weakest bond in each molecule was confirmed by the structure analysis, and its bond dissociation energy (BDE) was calculated.

Results and discussion

Infrared spectra :

IR spectrum is of significance for a compound to identify its structure. The frequencies of symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration for 16 ANs are shown in

Table 2. It is shown that the frequencies of symmetric stretching vibration of nitrate group (-ONO₂) for ANs increase (a hypsochromic shift) with the increasing of nitrate group numbers. Similarly, the frequencies of asymmetric stretching vibration of nitrate group for ANs increase (a hypsochromic shift) with the increasing of nitrate group numbers. The main reason may be an inductive effect.

Density and detonation property :

Detonation velocity (*D*), detonation pressure (*P*), and detonation heat (*Q*) are the important parameters to evaluate the performances of energetic compounds. However, density (ρ) and enthalpy of formation (ΔH_f) are of importance to calculate above detonation properties using the Kamlet-Jacobs formula¹⁵. The parameters for 16 ANs were listed in Table 3.

It can be seen that the density, detonation velocity, pressure, and heat are in direct proportion to the number of the nitrate group. In other words, for the sake of a higher energy density, we need more nitrate groups link with the adamantane to the best of our abilities.

BDE and stability :

The energy level difference, length and dissociation energy of the weakest O-N bond for 16 ANs are listed in Table 4. It can be seen that the number of nitrate group is in inverse proportion to the energy level difference and BDE, and in direct proportion to the length of the weakest O-N bond. It indicates that ANs' stabilities decrease with the increasing of the nitrate group number. In other words, for the sake of ANs' stabilities, we should decrease the number of nitrate group to the best of our abilities. It is similar to the most energetic compounds that the stability of ANs conflict with its energy and density. Consequently, we should balance the stability with energy and density when a new molecule is designed.

Table 2. Frequencies of symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration of nitrate group for 16 ANs calculated by B3LYP/6-31G** (in roman) and B3LYP/6-31G* (in italics) levels respectively

Compd.	Symmetric stretching vibration for ONO ₂ (cm ⁻¹)	Asymmetric stretching vibration for ONO ₂ (cm ⁻¹)
C1	1221; 1224; 1242 <i>1339; 1343; 1350</i>	1593; 1595 <i>1759; 1761</i>
C2	1211; 1220; 1223; 1226; 1231 <i>1333; 1341; 1344</i>	1598; 1604; 1605 <i>1766; 1771; 1772</i>
C3	1228; 1241; 1247; 1255 <i>1348; 1363; 1379</i>	1603; 1612; 1635; 1650 <i>1768; 1779; 1794; 1812</i>
C4	1217; 1221; 1225; 1236; 1244 <i>1343; 1349; 1361; 1365</i>	1598; 1602; 1606; 1636 <i>1763; 1766; 1769; 1773; 1812</i>
C5	1218; 1222; 1224; 1230 <i>1332; 1335; 1338; 1340; 1347</i>	1605; 1606; 1608; 1610 <i>1773; 1775; 1777; 1778</i>
C6	1208; 1219; 1237; 1239; 1245 <i>1344; 1350; 1362; 1366</i>	1602; 1609; 1613; 1641 <i>1767; 1771; 1775; 1778; 1808</i>
C7	1217; 1229; 1236; 1252 <i>1338; 1349; 1352; 1357</i>	1605; 1609; 1623; 1638; 1650 <i>1771; 1775; 1786; 1804; 1806</i>
C8	1219; 1222; 1225; 1229; 1235 <i>1334; 1336; 1338; 1339; 1349</i>	1615; 1618; 1621 <i>1775; 1776; 1783; 1786</i>
C9	1231; 1241; 1250 <i>1347; 1356; 1375; 1378</i>	1607; 1629; 1642; 1658 <i>1773; 1787; 1806; 1818; 1819</i>
C10	1218; 1227; 1235; 1242; 1254 <i>1344; 1353; 1356; 1361; 1380</i>	1611; 1628; 1633; 1646 <i>1776; 1790; 1795; 1808; 1812</i>
C11	1216; 1225; 123; 1235; 1238 <i>1336; 1339; 1344; 1346; 1354; 1380</i>	1617; 1619; 1624; 1670 <i>1783; 1785; 1788; 1790; 1828</i>
C12	1227; 1233; 1236; 1238; 1246 <i>1341; 1343; 1353; 1357; 1359; 1367</i>	1619; 1629; 1634; 1647; 1649 <i>1783; 1784; 1790; 1805; 1814</i>
C13	1239; 1249; 1251; 1256; 1260 <i>1354; 1360; 1365; 1372; 1379</i>	1630; 1634; 1641; 1646; 1651; 1660 <i>1790; 1794; 1800; 1810; 1821</i>
C14	1237; 1239; 1241; 1243; 1244 <i>1338; 1343; 1348; 1360; 1368; 1384</i>	1627; 1635; 1644; 1653; 1663 <i>1790; 1800; 1805; 1820; 1831</i>
C15	1236; 1243; 1246; 1252; 1255; 1262 <i>1360; 1365; 1368; 1373; 1378</i>	1635; 1642; 1657; 1664; 1669 <i>1796; 1801; 1804; 1817; 1823; 1831</i>
C16	1235; 1238; 1242; 1246; 1252; 1259 <i>1342; 1348; 1356; 1359; 1360; 1366</i>	1654; 1656; 1661; 1664 <i>1792; 1801; 1814; 1818; 1826; 1828</i>

Table 3. Densities, enthalpies of formation and detonation properties for 16 ANs on the basis of the results calculated by B3LYP/6-31G** (in roman) and B3LYP/6-31G* (in italics) levels respectively

Compd.	ρ (g cm ⁻³)	ΔH_f (kJ mol ⁻¹)	D (m s ⁻¹)	P (GPa)	Q (kJ kg ⁻¹)
C1	1.77	-639.90	7682	25.91	5241.0
	<i>1.81</i>	<i>-609.54</i>	<i>7836</i>	<i>27.33</i>	<i>5329.4</i>
C2	1.76	-653.21	7639	25.54	5206.1
	<i>1.79</i>	<i>-629.01</i>	<i>7765</i>	<i>26.68</i>	<i>5278.2</i>
C3	1.85	-572.82	7990	28.78	5417.6
	<i>1.80</i>	<i>-550.54</i>	<i>7873</i>	<i>27.53</i>	<i>5484.7</i>
C4	1.85	-730.20	8249	30.68	5599.0
	<i>1.89</i>	<i>-699.73</i>	<i>8400</i>	<i>32.20</i>	<i>5675.1</i>

Table-2 (contd.)

C5	1.97	-751.71	8608	34.64	5550.0
	<i>1.86</i>	<i>-726.79</i>	<i>8290</i>	<i>31.10</i>	<i>5613.3</i>
C6	1.97	-734.23	8939	37.35	6042.2
	<i>1.93</i>	<i>-702.76</i>	<i>8845</i>	<i>36.18</i>	<i>6110.5</i>
C7	2.06	-808.35	9176	40.34	5894.6
	<i>1.92</i>	<i>-773.83</i>	<i>8752</i>	<i>35.29</i>	<i>5968.9</i>
C8	1.92	-855.81	8687	34.76	5800.0
	<i>1.91</i>	<i>-831.51</i>	<i>8660</i>	<i>34.39</i>	<i>5854.0</i>
C9	2.06	-722.82	9241	40.92	6065.0
	<i>1.98</i>	<i>-686.21</i>	<i>9009</i>	<i>38.05</i>	<i>6143.0</i>
C10	2.02	-877.79	9248	40.12	6141.4
	<i>2.00</i>	<i>-842.12</i>	<i>9202</i>	<i>39.89</i>	<i>6209.3</i>
C11	2.02	-785.76	9312	41.10	6304.9
	<i>2.00</i>	<i>-760.00</i>	<i>9256</i>	<i>40.35</i>	<i>6355.2</i>
C12	2.03	-943.03	9450	42.45	6346.8
	<i>2.03</i>	<i>-913.20</i>	<i>9456</i>	<i>42.45</i>	<i>6398.3</i>
C13	2.05	-870.94	9561	43.70	6462.3
	<i>2.06</i>	<i>-841.86</i>	<i>9600</i>	<i>44.11</i>	<i>6512.7</i>
C14	2.03	-1002.27	9125	39.57	5518.7
	<i>2.04</i>	<i>-968.94</i>	<i>9191</i>	<i>40.29</i>	<i>5570.4</i>
C15	2.05	-937.22	9229	40.70	5613.7
	<i>2.12</i>	<i>-902.79</i>	<i>9466</i>	<i>43.55</i>	<i>5667.0</i>
C16	2.17	-1085.69	9249	42.14	4793.6
	<i>2.11</i>	<i>-1059.65</i>	<i>9076</i>	<i>39.98</i>	<i>4830.9</i>

Table 4. Energy level difference, length and dissociation energy of the weakest O-N bond for 16 ANs calculated by B3LYP/6-31G** (in roman) and B3LYP/6-31G* (in italics) levels respectively

Compd.	Energy level difference (eV)	Weakest O-N bond		
		Bond	Length (Å)	BDE (kJ mol ⁻¹)
C1	5.969	O31-N32	1.484	126
	<i>6.573</i>		<i>1.428</i>	<i>148</i>
C2	5.777	O25-N33	1.491	134
	<i>6.684</i>		<i>1.434</i>	<i>158</i>
C3	5.328	O24-N27	1.552	88
	<i>6.115</i>		<i>1.487</i>	<i>102</i>
C4	5.746	O25-N36	1.515	140
	<i>6.398</i>		<i>1.457</i>	<i>161</i>
C5	5.709	O26-N27	1.502	126
	<i>6.441</i>		<i>1.441</i>	<i>152</i>
C6	5.659	O21-N36	1.524	134
	<i>6.326</i>		<i>1.465</i>	<i>154</i>
C7	5.476	O22-N39	1.538	130
	<i>6.303</i>		<i>1.466</i>	<i>148</i>
C8	5.733	O21-N27	1.507	133
	<i>6.495</i>		<i>1.447</i>	<i>156</i>
C9	5.583	O22-N33	1.561	93
	<i>6.305</i>		<i>1.495</i>	<i>105</i>

Table-3 (contd.)

C10	5.426	O24-N36	1.538	103
	6.055		1.477	120
C11	5.214	O25-N39	1.579	83
	5.968		1.506	96
C12	5.500	O24-N27	1.536	120
	6.269		1.472	144
C13	5.413	O22-N39	1.563	93
	6.285		1.498	107
C14	5.418	O22-N30	1.558	116
	6.230		1.466	135
C15	5.416	O24-N42	1.577	91
	6.187		1.512	106
C16	5.453	O26-N27	1.556	119
	6.213		1.486	138

Conclusions

In the present work, quantum chemistry and Kamlet-Jacobs formula were employed to study the vibrational spectra, detonation properties, and stabilities of 16 adamantyl nitrates derivatives. It can be seen from the results that all frequencies of symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibrations of nitrate groups for ANs increase with the number of nitrate group. The number of the nitrate group is in direct proportion to the detonation properties. Conversely, it is in inverse proportion to the stability. Consequently, we should balance the stability with energy and density when a new molecule is designed.

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